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SOCIAL MEDIA IN TEACHING AND LEARNING- A STUDY

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Abstract

Social media tools are rapidly changing the communications landscape, Their emergence has impacted significantly how students learn and the way instructors teach. In today higher education settings, instructors, students and others collaborate on the tasks of knowledge construction.

The definition of social media is “the relationships that exist between network of people” [Walter & Riviera, 2004]. In the last ten years, the online world has changed dramatically. Thanks to the invention of social media, young men and women now exchange ideas, feelings, personal information, pictures and videos at a truly astonishing rate.

The influence of social media on teaching and learning environment is growing every year and its applications can reinforce class materials, positively influenced discussions, collaborative work, etc. The educators and researchers experimenting the social media technologies to stimulate collaboration, knowledge constructions and thinking skills.

This paper focuses on the broad picture of social media and the social factors affecting influence academic performance, a few students’ opinions on social media, and social media as a learning tool for the teaching professionals and for students.

Key words:- *Social media, students’ performance, learning tools, influence, academic performance, broad picture, students’ opinions.*

1. Introduction

The social media has become one of the most important communication means in recent times. However, social networking exists so as to provide communication among people regardless of the distance, making it open to people easily share information, files and pictures and videos, create blogs and send messages, and conduct real-time conversations. These systems are referred to as social, simply because they allow communication with buddies and coworkers so easily and effectively. It also strengthens the ties between people of those systems. In today's higher education settings, instructors, students and others collaborate on the task of knowledge construction. The favorites in the realm of internet sites are Facebook, Twitter, blogs, YouTube, instagram, google doc and others. These websites and social forums are way of communication directly with other people socially and in the media. They are playing a large and influential role decision-making in the occasions from the global world economically, politically, socially and educationally.

Social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, etc. connect people around the world in ways Marshall McLuhan could not have dreamed of when he popularized the term "global village" back in the 1960's. Fast forward 50 years and we find that the global village has indeed materialized, with new ideas and information being shared between people all over the world. Since education has always been about exposing people to new ideas, it's not surprising that the impact of social media is being felt in the education sector [12].

Schill [28] states that the social media sites encourage negative behaviors for teen students such as procrastination (catching up with friends), and themselves.... At present, whether social media is favorable or unfavorable, many students utilize these sites on a daily basis. As social media sites continue to grow in popularity, it is our belief that technology is a vital part of today's student success equation. Many researchers have been diving into a considerable amount of research on how social media influences student retention at colleges. Many parents are worried that their college students are spending too much time on Facebook and other social media sites and not enough time studying. Therefore, our research ascertains the relationship between the social media and students' study efficiency. It has been contended that, poor greater educational, social technologies support social constructivist techniques for learning, they potentially have to improve the students' construction of understanding and promote student interaction [1, 29 & 22]. An additional benefit of social technologies provided on the internet is

that they are frequently free or require marginal investment, eliminating a potential barrier to adoption [6]. There has been various overview and opinions which recognized four major advantages of social media use in higher education. These include, enhancing relationship, improving learning, motivation, offering personalized course material, and developing collaborative abilities [31 & 27]. This means that social networking activities have the possibility of enhancing student contact and is used to improve their participation in class, particularly where introverted students are involved. Students can function in online group learning, with less or no anxiety of needing to raise questions before peers at school [31].

2. Review of Literature

College students have great interest in social media. For the purpose of the study, social media was defined as Facebook, YouTube, Blogs, Twitter, MySpace, or LinkedIn [26].

Social media tools created a platform for the improvement of the educational process. To enrich the learning and teaching process with text, videos, and audio materials, the social media tools are useful, also it supports learning process of students and supports teachers in addition to the evaluation process [21].

The social media sites, mostly public web based services allow users to develop a personal profile, read and react on the postings on the site [11].

The individual users should restrict the information while posting on the media sites, also they should aware what information can be shared publicly. It includes favorite books, movies, birthdays, relationship status, etc. [31].

Students who may be reluctant to speak up in class or participating in book discussion blogs and writing for real audiences. There are new web tools emerging all the times that are enhancing learning [8]. The relationship between Facebook and well-being appears to become positive over the college years, possibly because upper class students use Facebook to connect socially with their peers and participate in college life [19].

Research in Humanities and Social Sciences www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1719 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2863 (Online) Vol.3, No.12, 2013 92 Young [34] in a study titled “the effect of internet use and social capital on the academic performance of students” observed that the internet expands its reach to teenagers’ school life. Young noted that students are more reliant on the internet to access information that is involved in school life as well as entertainment. The researcher further added that internet, though consumes time, has less effect on studies. Yang [32] notes the effect of social media depends large on the degree of usage. Yoon [33] observed that the type of social media or network subscribed to by a teenager exerts influence on him or her to visit the internet.

Education institution believes that social media sites offer value in teaching. It is also believed that video, podcast, and wiki’s are valuable tools for teaching, and a majority report that social media sites can be valuable tools for collaborative learning. [23].

Social media, throughout the communication world after 2005, has brought about the transformation of personal and social changes, with reference to youngsters between the ages of 13 to 25 who use the social media as a communication tool. Students could achieve more effective cooperation in their studies if they could make friends outside twitter groups, army friends and other traditional channels. Social media can be seen as one answer to this problem [30].

Just as college students are using social media websites like Facebook and Twitter to share their social lives online, new social media tools are ways these students can share their academic work online as well. Here is a rundown on social media tools college students can use from home or anywhere to book rentals.

3. Social media a broad picture

Social media in education include Facebook, Twitter, Linkedin, Google plus, message boards and blogging among which Facebook leads the rest. In 2008-2009 61% were of the population were using Facebook and it went up to 87% in 2009-10 and reached 98% in 2010-11. Educational institutes have been majorly using micro-blogging to update students and teachers with the latest announcements. From 0% use in 2008-09, the growth graph marked 59% in 2009-10 and finally 84% in 2011. The blogging has gained wide popularity over the years. It has had 48%, 46%, and 47% usage in years 2008-09, 2009-10 and 2010-11 respectively. Likewise the

message boards enjoyed a constant level of usage starting from 36% in 2008-09 to 38% in 2009-10 and 37% in 2010-11. Schools are adopting technologies for pedagogical purposes and introducing social media into the classroom. This is a trend that has garnered a lot of support as well as apprehension.

According to the study done by Mike Moran [23] the level of awareness among faculty does not vary with age or with a stage in career, the level of use does. Faculty with more experience are less likely to visit and less likely to post than are faculty that are early in their careers. Over 80% of faculty who have been teaching less than five years visited a social media site for personal use, and over 60% posted to at least one site during the survey period. This compares with only 70% of those who have been teaching more than 20 years and who visited a social media site for personal use within the survey period and with only 38% posted content.

4. Social Factors affecting influence academic performance

Dr Islam study has identified many factors that gave significant influence on students academic success. The factors are pre-admission qualification, time spent in studying, regular class attendance, probation status, father's education, parental support and involvement, interest in major subjects of study and the gender of the students as significant determinants of academic performance of the students [17].

When social media is used in pedagogy, students who have difficulty in expressing their thoughts in the classrooms can get involved in the learning process. This will help the students' confidence level.

Weisberger's hypothesis is supported by research by Junco, Heiberger and Loken [18] and Blaschke, Porto and Kurtez [7], which indicates that the active use of social media can increase learner engagement levels (student-student, student-instructor, and student-content) and promote the development of cognitive and meta-cognitive learning skills such as, reflection, critical thinking, construction of knowledge and understanding of ones individual learning process.

A pedagogical approach that aligns well with the use of social media eases that of *heutagogy*, the study of self determined learning, which places responsibility for the learning path in the hands

of the learner and where the learner is ‘the major agent in their own learning’ [15 & 16]. Research into the theory has shown that the approach can support development of lifelong learning capacity, as well as aid learners in managing and solving complex problems within changing environments [4, 3, 5, & 9].

5. Different types of social media

A few popular sites are given below:

1. Facebook: It creates a space for students to ask and answer questions. When students get home and begin working on their homework, they can post a question to the groups so as to get it answered by the group member.
2. It is also ideal for teachers using in flipped classroom. Post videos, photos, documents, and other resources on the group's wall and student can access before class or when they work on their assignments.

Twitter:

1. Twitter offers a quick way to post class announcements and reminders as well as real time information on class field trips.
2. It also helps classes track information on any topic. For instance, for a class discussing on a current event or a topic on career, twitter can provide up to date information, eliminating the need for extensive research.

3. Many organizations offer twitter chat sessions with which students can interact.

Blogs:

1. Instead of traditional writing projects, blogs creates opportunities for students to write and display their writings on a large scale.

YouTube:

1. It is like a Facebook, YouTube is an excellent option of flipping classroom in that students can watch lectures and resources before entering the classroom.

2. Again, like blogging, since the material will be seen by a wider audience, students will be more apt to do their very best in creating a video, and they will enjoy being able to express their creativity as they connect more deeply with the course material.

Instagarm:

1. “A picture is worth thousand words”. Instagram can showcase student work by offering a place to feature student hard work or even interesting details about a student.

Google Docs:

It is a popular technology with teachers and students. Students and teachers can use these tools to collaborate on assignments, projects, newsletters among other things. It allows more than one person to work on a particular document at the same time.

Google docs can promote the team work.

Student’s opinions

1. The students noted that it was difficult the learning activity from the media which supported this activity.

2. Active use of social media was viewed as encouraging deeper thinking, and social media compelled to process content and then to express it in various textual and visual forms.

3. Students not only used social media to complete their learning activities, but also to support the learning process itself.

4. Throughout the class, he used the social media to connect with his classmates outside the class. He communicated with the couple of classmates via Twitter, and the google chat. They swapped knowledge regarding the class, recommended sites and tools, and guideline each other through social media. It was wonderful to have this active network of students to communicate with and lean on for support throughout the class.

6. Advantages and Disadvantages of the social media

Like any other technological innovation, social media has its own advantages and disadvantages.

Advantages:

1. Social media enable students to easily contact with each other with regard to their projects and assignments.
2. Students also can work on group assignments from their home.
3. When social media is used in pedagogy students who have difficulty in expressing their thoughts in the classroom can get involved in the learning process, it helps to build their confidence level as well.
4. Any doubts can be clarified by posting a message through the social media.
5. A site like Facebook, etc. help teachers to stay in touch with the parents or so to know the progress of their children.
6. Students are learning the skill sets required for successful social networking.
7. Social media also brings with it the freedom for learners to connect and collaborate outside of institutional boundaries as well as to gain practical experience for the workforce [10 & 24].
8. Students are also being taught new concepts like online privacy.

In spite of the many advantages of the social media, there are some drawbacks which can affect the growth of the students as follows.

Disadvantages:

1. Students have become prone to frequent fluctuations in mood and self control.
2. A recent study has stated whenever someone uploads a profile picture, it immediately affects the mood of students. It produces stress, anxiety or fear for them.
3. Students neglect the studies by spending time on social networking website rather than studying or interacting with the people in person.
4. Students prefer to chat with the friends for the hours and this leads to the waste of time that could have been used for study or learning new skills.
5. Students' use of social media regularly may lose their ability to engage in face to face communication.
6. Even though students spend lots of time in socializing in an effective way, it should not hamper their study and academic credential. It should be kept in mind that the social networking creates the virtual world, that is drastically differ from the reality.

7. Conclusion

To conclude the teachers can communicate instantly and directly with the students and compare notes on education techniques, curriculum and teaching methodology and so on. Teachers, professors and academics routinely used blogs to write about the world of education and invite comments from all over the world.

The impact of social media is radically changing the way education has been traditionally delivered. Students should develop the cognitive and intuitive ability to analyze how much time they spent with social media. It is up to the students to decide what really matters in their life and how much of this virtual life translates to real life.

In spite of those concerns, however, the faculty believes a social media sites offer value in teaching. An overwhelming majority report that they believe that video, podcast, and wikis re

valuable tools for teaching, and a majority report that social media sites can be valuable tools for collaborative learning.

Time will tell whether the benefits outweigh the disadvantages, but one thing is certain, the social media are having and will continue to have a lasting impact on the educational field.

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